

Spectral and Electrical Conductance Studies of CT Complexes derived from 3-Amino-1,2,4-triazole Schiff Bases and Chloro-*p*-benzoquinone

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The solid CT complexes of some 3 aminotriazole Schiff bases with chloro *p*-benzoquinone derivatives are prepared and investigated by ir and electronic spectra. The spectral changes reveal that the CT interaction depends on the type of both the donor and acceptor. The change of electrical conductance with temperature for some CT complexes are also studied aiming to clarify their semiconductor characteristics

THE formation of molecular complexes of the charge transfer type between electron acceptors such as chloro-*p*-benzoquinones derivatives and π -electron donors was the subject of a number of investigations¹⁻⁹. Despite the fact that complexes of several donor molecules have been investigated, yet molecular complexes with heterocyclic Schiff bases as donors have not been included in the previous studies.

In the present article, the molecular compounds of some heterocyclic Schiff bases with chloro-*p*-benzoquinone derivatives have been prepared and investigated by ir and electronic spectra. To determine the suitability and efficiency as semiconductors, the electrical conductivity for some selected CT complexes has been measured.

Experimental

The donors used have the general structural formula :

1a; X=*p*-N(CH₃)₂, 1b; X=*p*-OCH₃, 1c; X=*p*-OH,
1d; X=*o*-OH, 1e; X=2-OH-1-naph, 1f; X=*p*-NO₂, 1g;
X=*p*-Br

The acceptors used are chloranil (2), 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-*p*-benzoquinone (3) and chloranilic acid (4).

The chemicals used in the present work were of pure grade (B.D.H.). The preparation of complexes and working procedure are the same as reported earlier^{10,11}.

The ir spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 1000 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a

Shimadzu 240 spectrophotometer. The electrical conductivity was measured on a RM 170 super megometer electrometer. The cross-section area of samples in the form of discs (1-3 mm × 13 mm dia) were painted with silver paste to eliminate the contact resistance between the probes and the discs. The temperature was measured in air using a Cu-CuNi thermocouple placed close to the samples.

Results and Discussion

The acceptor used involved the non-acidic chloranil (2) or dichlorodicyano-*p*-benzoquinone (3) and the acidic chloranilic acid (4). It is expected that the molecular compounds formed with acceptors 2 and 3 would be formed through electron transfer while acceptor 4 forms molecular compounds through proton and electron transfer. Based on this expectation, the molecular compounds formed with acceptor 4 are discussed separately.

Infrared spectra :

Molecular complexes with 2 and 3 : The spectra of this class can be considered as an overlap of the spectra of the components with some shifts in the bands. The bands of the donor parts are mostly shifted to higher wavenumbers whereas those of the acceptor molecules display a counter shift. The shifts of the ν_{CH} bands of the triazole ring are more pronounced than the ν_{CH} bands of the benzal ring with the exception of *p*-N(CH₃)₂ derivatives; for this donor, the shift of the ν_{OH} of the benzal ring is higher than that for the triazole ring. Based on this, the triazole ring is the origin of the CT donation for all compounds except 1a where the *p*-N(CH₃)₂ benzylidene ring is the donor centre. For the acceptor molecule, the C=O, C=C, C-C and C=N bands (Table 1) are shifted to lower wavenumbers as a result of the increased electron density on the acceptor in comparison to its free state. Accordingly the bonding between the donor and the

TABLE 1—IR, ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY FOR SOME CT COMPLEXES

Donor	Colour	M.p. °C	Ir spectra (cm ⁻¹)*				Electronic spectra			Activation energy	
			ν_{OH}	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{C\equiv N}$	δ_{OH}	<i>I</i>	λ_{Cr}	E_{Cr} Found/ (Calcd.)	ΔE_1	ΔE_2
Complexes with 2											
Bands of free acceptor											
1a	Olive green	130	—	1 694—1 682 1 770—1 665sh	—	—	7.74	420	2.96 (2.67)	1.28	0.26
1b	Brown	90	—	1 700—1 680	—	—	7.97	425	2.92 (2.90)	—	—
1e	Orange	172	—	1 690—1 630	—	—	7.82	460	2.70 (2.75)	1.09	0.53
1g	Buff	188	—	1 696—1 682	—	—	8.00	420	2.96 (2.61)	0.12	3.59
Complexes with 3											
Bands of free acceptor											
1	Dark grey	>250	—	1 695—1 678	2 325	—	—	—	—	1.29	0.78
1a	Red	62	—	1 694—1 665 1 685—1 642	2 230 2 180	—	8.33 7.74	500	2.49 (2.68)	1.52	—
1b	Brown	112	—	1 685—1 660	2 180sh	—	7.97	450	2.76 (2.09)	—	—
1c	Dark brown	130	—	1 688—1 672sh	2 220	—	7.92	540	2.30 (2.32)	—	—
1d	Dark brown	208	—	1 700—1 670	2 200	—	8.08	520	2.39 (2.27)	—	—
1e	Brown	120	—	1 680—1 635	2 180	—	7.82	520	2.39 (2.43)	1.25	4.24
1f	Brown	85	—	1 696—1 630	2 220	—	7.63	490	2.54 (2.17)	—	—
1g	Brown	57	—	1 700—1 662	2 220	—	8.00	—	—	—	—
Complexes with 4											
Bands of free acceptor											
1	Dark brown	211	3 235, 3 170 3 150	1 670—1 637 1 664—1 630	—	1 290, 1 270 1 273	8.33	480	2.58 (3.53)	0.74	2.38
1a	Bright black	154	3 160	1 600	—	1 280	7.74	490	2.53 (2.94)	0.12	1.71
1b	Brown	119	3 160	1 685—1 630	—	1 280	7.97	500	2.48 (3.17)	0.26	2.25
1c	Orange	92	3 200	1 675b	—	1 287	7.92	390	3.18 (3.12)	0.13	2.17
1d	Dark brown	204	3 200b	1 685—1 635	—	1 270	8.08	490	2.53 (3.28)	—	—
1e	Brown	130	3 160b	1 680—1 630	—	1 250	7.82	480	2.58 (3.02)	0.90	2.30
1f	Dark grey	87	3 150	1 665—1 632	—	1 270	7.63	510	2.43 (2.88)	—	—
1g	Brown	82	3 180	1 670—1 630	—	1 270	8.00	520	2.39 (3.20)	—	—

*b=band, sh=shoulder.

acceptor molecules may be formulated as :

where, $y=Cl$ for 2 and $y=CN$ for acceptor 3.

Molecular complexes with the acceptor 4 : This type of complex displays large changes in their ir spectra compared to those of their components.

The comparison reveals the presence of a group of medium bands within the wavenumber region 2300–3000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the stretching mode of a proton attached to a quaternary positive nitrogen, i.e. the structure $(\text{H}-\text{N}^+)$, formed through the proton transfer from one OH group of chloranilic acid to the basic centre on the donor molecule. Although more than one basic centre exist on the donor molecule, only one of the OH group is transformed to one basic centre. This is due to the fact that the negative charge on the oxygen of the ionised OH group of the acceptor would decrease the acidity of the second OH group leading to a lower probability for the transfer of the second proton from the acceptor to the donor molecule. This is further supported by the disappearance of only the bands due to different modes of vibrations of the weaker H-bonded OH group of chloranilic acid at 3235, 1270, and 1212 cm^{-1} , while those of the second OH group at 3170, 1290 and 1220 cm^{-1} are still observed in the spectra of the CT complexes. Also it seems that the basicity of the other centres on the donor is lowered under the influence of the $\equiv\text{NH}^+$ group. Due to the increased electron density on the acceptor ring, the various bands of the acceptor molecule (Table 1) exhibit a shift to lower values as a result of the $\pi-\pi^*$ electron transfer.

In the light of the results, the CT interaction with chloranilic acid can be formulated as follows:

Electronic absorption spectra :

The electronic absorption spectra of the CT complexes reveal the existence of new bands which are not observed in the absorption spectra of either the free donor or acceptor. However, the spectra display a single CT band within the range 480–540 nm corresponding to the $\pi-\pi^*$ intermolecular charge transfer interaction with $E_{CT}=2.30-3.18$ eV. The E_{CT} values obtained from the absorption spectra coincide fairly well with those obtained from the general equation¹²,

$$E_{CT} = I_p - (E_A + C)$$

where, E_A is the electron affinity of acceptors⁶ ($E_A^1=1.37, 1.95$ and 1.1 eV for acceptors 2, 3 and 4 respectively), I_p the ionisation potential values of the free donor and C the coulombic factor between the electron transferred and the positive hole left behind ($C=3.7$ eV³). The appearance of one band denotes that no $n-\pi^*$ interaction is liable to occur (Table 1).

Electrical conductivity measurements :

I-V data for different CT complexes were measured at room temperature. A satisfactory linear relationship is obtained which indicates that the CT complexes have ohmic character. The variation of DC electrical conductivity as a function of the reciprocal of the absolute temperature for the various solid CT complexes shows a good linearity with a negative slope (Fig. 1) which is in accordance with the known relation. This proves that these compounds have a semiconducting character in the

Fig. 1. Variation of electrical conductivity as a function of reciprocal absolute temperature for chloranilic acid CT complexes with donors: (●) 1b and (×) 1c.

temperature range investigated. From this linear relationship the activation energy (ΔE) was then calculated (Table 1). Fig. 1 shows two inflections for all compounds except that of 1a with acceptor 3. This denotes that the mode of conduction probably changed during conductivity measurements. The first part of the curve is due to electronic conduction through the delocalisation of the π -electron. At higher temperature, in the second part, the conduction would be due to the excitation of an electron from the uppermost filled π -molecular orbital to the lowest unfilled π -molecular orbital. Thus, the electron is assumed to tunnel to an equivalent empty level of a neighbouring molecule in the anodic

direction whereas the positive hole moves to a molecule in the cathodic direction.

For the CT complexes of donor **1e** with acceptors 2-4, ΔE value of the complexes was found to increase from acceptor 4 to 3. The low value of ΔE for chloranilic acid complex is in accordance with the fact that the molecular complex of 4 is formed through electron and proton transfer. For

Fig. 2. Variation of ΔE for some CT complexes of chloranilic acid with different donors as a function of I_p of the donors.

the chloranil complexes with donors **1e** and **1f**, the presence of NO_2 group in donor **1f** will facilitate the charge delocalisation and thus the conductivity increases. Consequently, the activation energy of the complex with donor **1f** is lower than that of the complex with donor **1e**.

The electrical conductivity and the activation energies of CT complexes of chloranilic acid would be dependent on the ionisation potential of the donors. Fig. 2 shows the plot of I_p of donor with ΔE of different CT complexes which appears linear with positive slope. This could be explained on the basis of the increased electron density and polarisation of the donor molecules as a function of the electron donating or attracting character of the substituent. Thus, donor substituents enhance the ionisation mechanism and electron flow.

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